

A new species of *Pyrenaearia* (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) from the Pyrenees

Una nueva especie de *Pyrenaearia* (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) de los Pirineos

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ABSTRACT

A new species of the land snail genus *Pyrenaearia* from the Pyrenees, previously recognized combining multilocus genetic data with techniques of 3D geometric morphometrics on the shell, is described here and named as *Pyrenaearia guillenae* n. sp. We provide information about the species diagnosis, distribution and habitat and assess its threat status as Near Threatened according to IUCN criteria.

RESUMEN

Una nueva especie del género de caracoles terrestres *Pyrenaearia*, previamente reconocida tras combinar datos genéticos multilocus con técnicas de morfometría geométrica en 3D en la concha, se describe bajo el nombre *Pyrenaearia guillenae* n. sp. Proporcionamos aquí información acerca de la diagnosis de la especie, así como de su distribución y hábitat, y concluimos que su estado de conservación debe considerarse como Casi Amenazada siguiendo los criterios de la UICN.

INTRODUCTION

The land snail genus *Pyrenaearia* Hesse, 1921 is endemic to the northern Iberian Peninsula with a discontinuous distribution across the Cantabrian Mountains, the Pyrenees, the pre-littoral mountain system of Catalonia and the Mount Moncayo (ORTIZ DE ZÁRATE, 1956; PUENTE, 1994). The genus is a rock-dwelling specialist further restricted to shady environments and, therefore, their populations are limited to north faces or very abrupt terrains and cliffs of mountainous areas

of calcareous substrate (PRIETO, 1986; PUENTE, 1994), with the exception of *P. navasi* (Fagot, 1907) which inhabits in siliceous substrate (PRIETO, 1991).

Because the genus is anatomically conservative (ORTIZ DE ZÁRATE, 1956), and due to its recent and rapid speciation (ELEJALDE ET AL., 2009), solving its taxonomy is challenging. First, morphological differentiation of the species is restricted to shell characters which are known to be highly correlated with envi-

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ronmental factors and can led to local adaptations that may blur taxonomy (FIORENTINO *ET AL.*, 2008; RAZKIN *ET AL.*, 2016; STANKOWSKI, 2011, 2013). Secondly, the rapid and recent speciation of the genus may also hinder species delimitation due to incomplete lineage sorting (EDWARDS & KNOWLES, 2014). To overcome these problems, CARO, GÓMEZ-MOLINER & MADEIRA (2019) carried out an integrative species delimitation approach on the genus combining multi-locus genetic data with 3D geometric morphometrics techniques on the shell. In that work the authors reviewed taxonomy of the genus and identified ten species distributed in clades G1 to G9 (with two molecularly indiscernible but morphologically distinct species in clade G1). There was no available name for one of the species of *Pyrenaearia* from the Pyrenees distributed in Aigüestortes and Andorra (clade G8), and the purpose of the present paper is to provide a formal name for its taxonomic recognition.

The integration of multiple lines of evidence is widely recognized as indispensable to properly delimit species (PADIAL *ET AL.*, 2010) and, as its application increased, so does the discovery of new species. However, it has been noticed that several of these new species are not accompanied by formal species description (PANTE, SCHOELINCK & PUILLANDRE, 2015). Naming new species is fundamental to link the data from different sources referring to them and to build new knowledge about them (PATTERSON *ET AL.*, 2010), as it is also essential to describe biodiversity (PANTE *ET AL.*, 2015). Here we provide a formal description, determine the distribution and assess the threat status of the newly discovered species of *Pyrenaearia*, *P. guillenae* n. sp., to ensure its recognition by scientific community, governments (environmental managers) and non-scientist audience.

SYSTEMATICS

Family HYGROMIIDAE Tryon, 1866
Subfamily LEPTAXINAE Boettger, 1909
Genus *Pyrenaearia* Hesse, 1921

MATERIAL AND METHODS

For the anatomical study of the species, four specimens from the type locality drowned in water and preserved in 70% ethanol were dissected using a Nikon SMZ-U (Zoom 1:10) and drawings were made with the assistance from a Nikon drawing tube. Their shells were photographed with a Nikon D3100 (objective Tamron SP AF 90mm f/2.8 Di Macro) at different depth and then they were merged with CombineZM (HADLEY, 2008) to obtain fully focused photos. Shells from all the known populations (n = 38) were measured with a digital caliper (Ratio 6369H15) for the maximum and minimum diameter and for height to record the variability of the shell across all the distribution range. Shell whorls were counted following KERNEY & CAMERON (1979).

To diagnose the species molecularly, we searched for synapomorphies in DNA sequences. Nucleotide apomorphic substitutions were mapped along the consensus tree obtained by CARO *ET AL.* (2019) based on their sequence alignment containing the mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI) and 16S RNA ribosomal subunit (16S), along with the nuclear gene cluster consisting of the loci *ITS1-5.8S-ITS2-28S*, using the command 'describtrees / plot=cladogram opt=deltran apolist = yes' in PAUP* (SWOFFORD, 2002).

We applied the IUCN criteria (IUCN, 2012; 2017) to assess the threat status of *P. guillenae* n. sp. Extent of occurrence (EOO) was calculated as the minimum convex polygon (the smallest polygon in which no internal angles exceeds 180 degrees and which contains all the sites of occurrence). Area of occupancy (AOO) was estimated by considering an area of 2x2 km for each of the occupied UTM grid cells (IUCN, 2012).

Figure 1. Frontal (left), superior (middle) and inferior (right) views of *Pyrenaearia guillenae* n. sp. shells. A: Holotype; B: Paratype 1; C: Paratype 2, all from the type locality.

Figura 1. Vistas frontal (izquierda), superior (centro) e inferior (derecha) de conchas de Pyrenaearia guillenae n. sp. A: Holotipo; B: Paratipo 1; C: Paratipo 2, todas de la localidad tipo.

Pyrenaearia guillenae n. sp. (Figs. 1-3)

Type material: Holotype, collected the 30th of July of 2014 by Glòria Guillén and Jordi Corbella, is deposited in the collection of the Museum of Natural Sciences of Madrid with catalog number MNCN15.05.200023H; forepart of the body in 70% ethanol, a small portion of foot in 96% ethanol for molecular analyses and shell kept separately; GenBank accession numbers of amplified DNA sequences: MG593766 (cytochrome c oxidase subunit I, mitochondrial), MG593767 (16S RNA ribosomal subunit, mitochondrial) and MG593768 (ITS1-5.8S-ITS2-28S gene cluster, nuclear).

Paratypes: All deposited in the collection of the Museum of Natural Sciences of Madrid. From the type locality (MNCN15.05.200023P): 3 individuals with forepart of the body in 70% ethanol, a small portion of foot in 96% and shell kept separately (Paratypes 1-3); 1 specimen in 96% ethanol (Paratype 4); and 6 shells (Paratype 5). From Lo Forcallet, Montanyó de Llacs (MNCN15.05.200024): 1 specimen in 96% ethanol (Paratype 6); and 1 shell (Paratype 7). From Muntanya de Casamanya (MNCN15.05.200025): 2 individuals in 96% ethanol (Paratypes 8-9).

Type locality: Canal de les Estanyeres, Aigüestortes (Serra de les Agudes, Pyrenees, Lleida province, Spain); UTM: 31T 0339763 4718950; altitude: 2300 m; glacier bucket in which marble clasts predominate, with little vegetation and a slight slope facing towards northeast.

Etymology: The species epithet *guillenae* is a noun formed from the personal name Guillén after Glòria Guillén who along with Jordi Corbella found two of the known populations, including the type locality.

Figure 2. Anatomy of genitalia in *Pyreanaearia guillenae* n. sp. based on the holotype. Abbreviations, bc: bursa copulatrix; dbc: duct of bursa copulatrix; ds: dart sac; e: epiphallus; f: flagellum; ga: genital atrium; mg: mucus gland; p: penis; prm: penial retractor muscle; sod: spermoviduct; v: vagina; vd: vas deferens.

Figura 2. Anatomía del genital en Pyreanaearia guillenae n. sp. basada en el holotipo. Abreviaturas, bc: bolsa copulatrix; dbc: conducto de la bolsa copulatrix; ds: saco del dardo; e: epifalo; f: flagelo; ga: atrio genital; mg: glándula mucosa; p: pene; prm: músculo retractor del pene; sod: espermoviducto; v: vagina; vd: vaso deferente.

Description: Adult shell (Fig. 1) relatively thin, globular to somewhat depressed, with 4.75–5.5 whorls ($n = 14$). Maximum breadth 10.5–12.5 mm, minimum breadth 9.1–10.5 mm and height 6.1–8.2 mm ($n = 38$ for all measures). Body world expanded regularly, rounded to slightly angulated at the beginning, rounded near the aperture and slightly descending towards the opening. Umbilicus very narrow, circular and deep, representing 1/10 of maximum shell width, partially covered by columellar edge. Oblique and oval aperture, with marginal ends somewhat convergent. Peristome thin throughout, plane except at the base, being widely reflected towards the umbilicus. Peristome is sometimes slightly thickened inside, close to the opening. Shell surface with irregular transversal striae and with a faint spiral microsculpture. Background colour light brown to brown, with many radial, narrow, whitish bands, varying in density all along the teleoconch. There is a conspicuous

whitish carenal band in the periphery of the shell. Protoconch uniformly brown.

Genital anatomy (Fig. 2), based on dissection of four mature animals. Genital atrium short, with similar width to vagina. Penis moderately long (5–7 mm), cylindrical, enlarged in the central part indicating the position of the verge. Penial retractor muscle inserted at the proximal end of penis indicating the separation with epiphallus. Epiphallus as long as penis, coiled, slightly narrower than penis, becoming narrower towards its distal end. Flagellum (4–6 mm) shorter and narrower than epiphallus, with the half distal portion very narrow. Vagina cylindrical, of similar length to penis, often somewhat narrower or with the same width than penis. Dart sac complex showing a double structure, with two muscular sacs of similar size, closely linked together and placed on the same side of vagina. External sac containing a dart. Six to eight digitiform glands in four groups (usually bifurcated) inserting near the proximal part of vagina. Duct of

Figure 3. Distribution of the *Pyrenaearia* species from the Axial Pyrenees. On the top right zoom with the distribution of *Pyrenaearia guillenae* n. sp. 1: Canal de les Estanyeres, Aigüestortes; 2: Rocablanca, Aigüestortes; 3: Lo Forcallet, Montanyó de Llacs, Aigüestortes; 4: Muntanya de Casamanya.

Figura 3. Distribución de las especies de *Pyrenaearia* del eje axial de los Pirineos. En la esquina superior derecha zoom indicando la distribución de *Pyrenaearia guillenae* n. sp. 1: Canal de les Estanyeres, Aigüestortes; 2: Rocablanca, Aigüestortes; 3: Lo Forcallet, Montanyó de Llacs, Aigüestortes; 4: Muntanya de Casamanya.

bursa copulatrix cylindrical, long (10–12 mm), moderately wide. Bursa oval, thin walled.

Diagnosis: The genital anatomy described here unequivocally places *P. guillenae* n. sp. within *Pyrenaearia*, but as it has been reported for the genus (ORTIZ DE ZÁRATE, 1956), it is unable to distinguish it from the other genus species. The shell is easily differentiated from those of *P. cantabrica* (Hidalgo, 1873), *P. oberthueri* (Ancey, 1884) and *P. daanidentata* Raven, 1988 which instead of a narrow umbilicus present a wide one and also from the more flattened shell of *P. molae* Haas, 1924 and *P. organiaca* (Fagot, 1905). Further, it can not be confused with the shell of *P. parva* Ortiz de Zárate, 1956 smaller, with a wider umbilicus and strong striation, nor with the fragile and uniformly brown *P. navasi* (Fagot, 1907). However, with the naked eye the shell of this species and those of *P. cotiellae* (Fagot, 1906), *P. carascalensis* (Férussac, 1821) and *P. carascalopsis* (Bourguignat in Fagot, 1884) are not discernible since they share the same overall shape and

colouration and striation patterns and these species can only be delimited morphologically when fine geometric morphometric techniques are applied (CARO ET AL., 2019). Nevertheless, molecular characters are able to unequivocally diagnose *P. guillenae* n. sp. and separate it from the rest. Within the genus, considering only the apomorphic nucleotide substitutions with high consistency index (CI > 0.65), *P. guillenae* n. sp. is characterized by apomorphic changes in cytochrome c oxidase subunit I gene: A→T in 78 base pair (bp) (CI = 1.00), T→C in 114 bp (CI = 0.75) and T→C in 189 bp (CI = 0.67). Besides, the species can be distinguished from its sibling species *P. cotiellae* due to the apomorphic substitution of T→C (CI = 1.00) this last species presents in the 946 position of the ITS1-5.8S-ITS2-28S nuclear gene cluster.

Distribution: The species is known from four populations (Fig. 3). Three are present in Aigüestortes (Leida) in Canal de les Estanyeres, Rocablanca and Lo Forcallet and the fourth is located in Andorra in Muntanya de Casamanya.

Table I. U.T.M. and altitude of the known populations of *Pyrenaearia guillenae* n. sp.
 Table I. U.T.M.s y altitud de las poblaciones conocidas hasta la fecha de *Pyrenaearia guillenae* n. sp.

Locality	Province	Country	HUSO	X	Y	Altitude (m)
Canal de les Estanyeres, Aigüestortes	Lleida	Spain	31T	339763	4718950	2300
Rocablanca, Aigüestortes	Lleida	Spain	31T	339326	4718268	2519
Lo Forcallet, Montanyó de Llacs, Aigüestortes	Lleida	Spain	31T	328536	4711093	2184
Muntanya de Casamanya	Ordino	Andorra	31T	382653	4715934	2600

Exact location of the populations is listed in Table I.

Habitat: Shady screes and rock walls of calcareous materials, under stones or directly glued to the rocks. It inhabits above 2100 m.

Assessment of threat status: From the five IUCN criteria used to evaluate the threat category of a taxon, (A: Population size reduction; B: Geographic range; C: Small population size and decline; D: Very small or restricted population; E: Quantitative analysis), there is only information of criteria B and D. There are no studies about population size or trends, but field observations indicate that population trend is stable. Besides, the largest population of the species (three of the four known sites) lives in a protected area, the National Park of Aigüestortes i Estany de Sant Maurici, meaning that all these sites are under the protection of national and regional environmental guidelines.

For criterion B three conditions have to be met simultaneously: small geographic range (EOO and/or AOO) together with severely fragmented population or small number of locations, continuous decline or extreme fluctuations. EOO and AOO are very restricted (185.4 km² and 12 km², respectively) while the number of locations is limited to 4 sites and the population is fragmented (living above 2100 m). Nevertheless, there are no evidences of continuous decline or extreme fluctuations in EOO, AOO, number of subpopulations or number of mature individuals. Hence, the species only meets two conditions of this criterion. On the other hand, the species covers the criterion D2 to be

assessed as Vulnerable: AOO less than 20 km² or number of locations equal to or less than five (IUCN, 2012). However, the restricted area of occupancy under criterion D2 (IUCN, 2017, page 69) "is defined such that the population is prone to the effects of human activities or stochastic events in an uncertain future, and is thus capable of becoming Critically Endangered or even Extinct in a very short time period (e.g., within one or two generations after the threatening event occurs)". It is not plausible that *P. guillenae* n. sp. could become Critically Endangered or Extinct in a short time. Further, IUCN guidelines (IUCN, 2017, page 69) state that "if the taxon is highly restricted, and there are plausible threats that can cause the species to become Vulnerable or Endangered in a short time, then the taxon should be considered for listing as Near Threatened". Being a species living only above 2100 m, global warming could represent a major threat for *P. guillenae* n. sp. Thus, according to criterion D2, this species is assessed as Near Threatened.

Some of the records historically assigned to *P. carascalensis* (ALTIMIRA, 1965, 1994; ELEJALDE ET AL., 2009; PUENTE, 1994) are now attributed to *P. guillenae* n. sp. (see Fig. 3 with the distribution of the *Pyrenaearia* species from the Axial Pyrenees). Even though *P. carascalensis* has been split into two species and its geographical range is now restricted to the western Pyrenees and East Cantabrian Mountains (EOO = 1659.2 km², estimated adding the EOO areas of the two populations as shown in Fig. 3), we propose to maintain its current threat status as Least Concern (GÓMEZ-MOLINER, 2011).

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